

D4.1 Datasets description

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Executive Summary

The following document is ‘Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description’ in the framework of the project titled ‘Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women’s inclusion in transport systems.’ (Acronym: DIAMOND; Grant Agreement No 824326).

The document describes the datasets collected through the activities of ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’¹ (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020), focusing on each Use Case of DIAMOND:

- Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Data collection campaigns have been based on the methodological approach of the DIAMOND project². This relies on the Fairness Characteristics (FCs) identified through Thematic Analysis and on a series of interdisciplinary tools and methods (as listed below). The heterogeneous and disaggregated datasets gathered through the executed data collection campaigns are classified in three main categories:

- Thematic analysis:
 - Literature review (All Use Cases);
 - Focus Groups (All Use Cases);
 - Semi structured interview (All Use Cases).
- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Structured data (Use Cases I, III and IV);
 - Observations (Use Cases I, II and III);
 - Users and Employers’ Satisfaction Index questionnaires (all Use Cases);
 - Social media data (Use Cases I, II and III).
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data:
 - Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (all Use Cases).

Deliverable 4.1 is aimed at reporting the datasets collected for the DIAMOND project including information about the identification of dataset sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and responsible partners of the Consortium for each data collection activity.

Within the objectives of the ‘Work Package 4 – Interdisciplinary model creation’, the Service and Employers’ Database will be analysed using Regression Analysis and Bayesian Networks, while the Users and Employees Perception Database will be analysed using Analytic Hierarchy Processes.

¹ See ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’.

² See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’ and ‘Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy’.

Deliverable 4.1 is especially useful for:

- WP4 Interdisciplinary Model Creation;
- WP5 DIAMOND Toolbox Development;
- WP6 DIAMOND Testing and Validation;
- WP8 Ethical, Legal and Data Management.

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Terminology and Acronyms

ADAS	Advanced Driving Assistance System
ADS	Automated Driving System
AITEC	Aitec Asesores Internacionales srl
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
API	Application Programming Interface
AV	Automated Vehicles
BN	Bayesian Network
CBI-R	Career Barriers Inventory-Revised
CCTV	Closed-circuit Television
CF	Concept of Fairness
CFCs	Cluster of Fairness Characteristics
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DAD	Dynamic Argumentative Delphi
DDT	Dynamic Driving Tasks
ENU	Edinburgh Napier University
EU	European Union
EURECAT	Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Cataluña
FCs	Fairness Characteristics
FGC	Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Cataluña
FTTE	University of Belgrade
G&V	Genre et Ville
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAV	Highly Automated Vehicles
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HR	Human Resources
IBV	Instituto de Biomecánica
ID	Inclusion Diamond
IPs	Influencing Parameters
M	Month
OAPs	Old Age Pensioners
OSM	Open Street Map
PI	Polyhedral Individual
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
RINA	Rina Services spa
SD	Standard Deviation
STIR	University of Stirling
SYS	Systematica srl
TU Dublin	Technological University Dublin

UESI	<i>Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires</i>
UC1	<i>Use Case I</i>
UC2	<i>Use Case II</i>
UC3	<i>Use Case III</i>
UC4	<i>Use Case IV</i>
VELIB	<i>Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib Métropole</i>
WAVE	<i>Wave Women and Vehicles in Europe</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
ZTM	<i>Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa (Public Transport Authority)</i>

I. Introduction

The current document ‘Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description’ describes the data collected through the ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’³ of the DIAMOND project (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020). In this regard, the document includes information regarding the identification of dataset sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and responsible partners of the Consortium for each data collection activity.

The main objective of the DIAMOND project is to turn data into reliable and actionable knowledge for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees. The document is focused on **four Use Cases**⁴:

- Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Within the objectives of the ‘Work Package 2 – Conceptual Framework’ and ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’, data collection campaigns were executed on the basis of: the Inclusion Diamond representation⁵, the concept of Polyhedral individual⁶, the Concept of Fairness⁷ and the **methodological approach**⁸ of the DIAMOND Project (see Figure I The methodological approach for the data collection of the DIAMOND Project.). This was aimed at collecting **heterogeneous and disaggregated data** about women’s needs in the transport sector, as users and employees. The gathered datasets are divided into three main categories:

- **Thematic analysis:**
 - Literature review (Use Case I, II, III and IV);
 - Focus groups (Use Case I, II, III and IV);
 - Semi-structured Interviews (Use Case I, II, III and IV).
- **Service and Employers’ Provision Data:**
 - Structured data regarding the operation of transport services (Use Cases I and III) and job holders of the sector (Use Case IV);
 - Observations regarding relevant features of transportation settings (Use Cases I and III) and emotional responses to autonomous vehicles (Use Case II);
 - Users and Employees’ Satisfaction Index questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III) and job conditions and employability (Use Case IV);

³ See ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’.

⁴ See ‘Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition’.

⁵ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁶ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁷ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁸ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’ and ‘Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy’.

- Social media data from Twitter regarding geospatial/time-based information and the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III).
- **Users and Employees' Perception Data:**
 - DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires regarding the Fairness Characteristics (Use Cases I, II, III and IV).

As a preliminary step towards data collection, the methodological approach of the DIAMOND Project was based on the identification of a series of Fairness Characteristics (FCs) related to the inclusion of women in the transport sector.

FCs were defined and validated through a **Thematic Analysis**⁹, which was based on a review of the most relevant scientific literature and on the execution of a series of focus groups for each Use Case which were conducted in order to achieve a cross national comparison to ensure all meanings were similar and the data being collected was suitable to answer the research question(s).

Additional semi-structured interviews were seen as necessary in the mid-term of the DIAMOND's project to gather deeper data for the interdisciplinary analysis, especially for specific profiles. This dataset was classified as "Users and Employees' perception data".

All data collection activities have been conducted once ethical approval has been granted locally and by **following a rigid ethical framework of conducting social research**¹⁰.

As per the research ethics guidelines set out by Horizon 2020 and the intuitions of consortium partners, the data collected will be stored in several formats (e.g., documents, images, videos, data, numerical codes, maps and models). The following table provides an overview of file types for sharing, reuse and preservation¹¹.

Type of data	Acceptable formats for sharing, reuse and preservation	Other acceptable formats for data preservation
Tabular data with extensive metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SPSS portable format (.por) • delimited text and command ('setup') file (SPSS, Stata, SAS, etc.) • structured text or mark-up file of metadata information (e.g., DDI XML) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • proprietary formats of statistical packages: SPSS (.sav), Stata (.dta), • MS Access (.mdb/.accdb)
Tabular data with minimal metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • comma-separated values (.csv) • tab-delimited file (.tab) • delimited text with SQL data definition statements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • delimited text (.txt) with characters not present in data used as delimiters • widely-used formats: MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), MS Access (.mdb/.accdb), dBase (.dbf), OpenDocument Spreadsheet (.ods)

⁹ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

¹⁰ See 'Deliverable 8.1 Data Management Plan' and 'Deliverable 8.2 Guide to interview and ethics'.

¹¹ See 'Deliverable 8.1.2 Data Management Plan revision period I'

Geospatial data vector and raster data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESRI Shapefile (.shp, .shx, .dbf, .prj, .sbx, .sbn optional) • geo-referenced TIFF (.tif, .tiff) • CAD data (.dwg) • tabular GIS attribute data • Geography Markup Language (.gml) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESRI Geodatabase format (.mdb) • MapInfo Interchange Format (.mif) for vector data • Keyhole Mark-up Language (.kml) • Adobe Illustrator (.ai), CAD data (.dxf or .svg) • binary formats of GIS and CAD packages
Qualitative textual data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich Text Format (.rtf) • plain text, ASCII (.txt) • extensible Mark-up Language (.xml) text according to an appropriate Document Type Definition (DTD) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypertext Mark-up Language (.html) • widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx) • some software-specific formats: NUD*IST, NVivo and ATLAS.ti
Image data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TIFF 6.0 uncompressed (.tif) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • JPEG (.jpeg, .jpg, .jp2) if original created in this format • GIF (.gif) • TIFF other versions (.tif, .tiff) • RAW image format (.raw) • Photoshop files (.psd) • BMP (.bmp) • PNG (.png) • Adobe Portable Document Format (PDF/A, PDF) (.pdf)
Audio data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free Lossless Audio Codec (.flac) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-I Audio Layer 3 (.mp3) if original created in this format • Audio Interchange File Format (.aif) • Waveform Audio Format (.wav)
Video data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MPEG-4 (.mp4) • OGG video (.ogv, .ogg) • motion JPEG 2000 (.mj2) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AVCHD video (.avchd)
Documentation and scripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rich Text Format (.rtf) • PDF/UA, PDF/A or PDF (.pdf) • XHTML or HTML (.xhtml, .htm) • OpenDocument Text (.odt) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • plain text (.txt) • widely-used formats: MS Word (.doc/.docx), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx) • XML marked-up text (.xml) according to an appropriate DTD or schema

Table 1. File formats recommended for data sharing, reuse and preservation

Within the objectives of the ‘Work Package – Interdisciplinary model creation’, the collected Service and Employers’ Database will be analysed using **Regression Analysis, Factor Analysis, Regression Trees** and **Bayesian Networks**, while the Users and Employees Perception Database will be analysed using **Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)**.

- **Regression analysis** is a technique used to model and analyse the relationship between variables and how they contribute and are related to producing a particular outcome together. This analysis will be used as a starting building point to the Bayesian Network;
- **Factor analysis** is used to reduce the complexity of the dataset grouping together the questions that tend to follow similar patterns;
- **Regression trees** estimates the values of user satisfaction according to demographic characteristics of the users;
- **Bayesian Networks** determine the existence or not of relationships between different variables and which variables have higher importance. This analysis allows to get in a graphical form (or network structure) relationship between variables that quantifies the importance of each variable in achieving the goal of each use case;
- **Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)** establish a hierarchy among multiple criteria through the obtainment of the weight of each criterion using the AHP method. DIAMOND project uses Fuzzy AHP (FAHP) instead of classical AHP method in order to consider the fuzziness and vagueness of respondents. Not considering the fuzziness of some decision-making problems can contribute to imprecise judgements in conventional AHP method.

Deliverable D4.I is aimed at reporting information about the Thematic Analysis (see Annex 1) and the results of our data collection campaigns. The results of the data collection campaigns of the DIAMOND Project are presented in the following Sections, with reference to Use Case I (Section 2), Use Case II (Section 3), Use Case III (Section 4) and Use Case IV (Section 5). The information regarding the collected datasets is described in Annex 2 (Use Case I), Annex 3 (Use Case III) and Annex 4 (Use Case IV).

1.1 Thematic Analysis

The Thematic Analysis was aimed at identifying and validating a series of **Fairness Characteristics (FCs)** through the review of the most relevant scientific literature and the execution of several Focus Groups to further test the fairness principles related to ‘Inclusiveness for Women Users and Employees in Transport Sector’.

The **Literature Review**¹² aimed to identify a series of FCs for each Use Case¹³ (Level 2), which were later grouped into several Clusters of Fairness Characteristics (CFCs – Level 1). Then, a series of Influencing Parameters (IPs – Level 3) were identified for each FC. Literature reviews were conducted by the consortium partners through several academic database (e.g., Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar, Research Gate) and organized in a tabular structure based on a collaborative Excel worksheet (see Annex 1).

¹² See ‘Deliverable 3.I Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

¹³ Responsible partners: SYS (Use Case I); AITEC (Use Case II); ENU (Use Case III); STIR (Use Case IV).

The identified FCs were then analysed using chi-squared test (χ^2) and Cramer's V to validate statistically significant relationships between two nominal (categorical) variables¹⁴. or FCs (see D3.3 Report on data collection campaigns).

Based on preliminary focus group performed by TU Dublin and STIR in Dublin (Ireland) on April 2019-M6 (see Annex I), a series of further **Focus Groups** were executed in Paris (G&V), Barcelona (FGC) and Warsaw (ZTM) from March 2020 (M17) to November 2020 (M25), focusing on 'Inclusiveness for Women Users and Employees in Transport Sector' (see Annex I). Data were collected on each Use Case and from across partner countries in order to provide robust cross-cultural findings to validate the identified FCs.

Semi-structured Interviews were seen as necessary in the mid-term of the DIAMOND's project to gather deeper data for the interdisciplinary analysis, especially for specific profiles (ongoing data collection activity).

¹⁴ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

Figure 1 The methodological approach for the data collection of the DIAMOND Project.

2. Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)

2.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case I ‘Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)’ is to **investigate women’s needs as users of metro and urban railway infrastructures** and is aimed at supporting the development of gender-equitable transport planning and design policies. The final goal of the Use Case I is to increase the percentage of women using metro and commuter railway public transports.

The **methodology for data collection**¹⁵ for the Use Case I consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Structured data regarding the transport settings and the operation of the service;
 - Observations regarding universal design indicators of the infrastructures;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers’ Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were collected focusing on the metro and commuter urban railway stations managed by **FGC-Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya** (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and by **ZTM-Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa** (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland). Users and Employees’ Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several **European Countries**.

2.2 Service and Employers’ Provision Data (Use Case I)

2.2.1 Structured Data (Use Case I)

Structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M17-March 2020) was aimed at selecting and characterizing a sample of 10 suitable stations managed by **FGC** (82 stations in total) and 10 stations managed by **ZTM** (96 stations in total).

In order to identify specific stations to be used, **Structured Open Data** were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open data repositories, national geoportals and census databases (see Annex 2). Preliminary structured open data analysis was based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS). A series of thematic maps¹⁶ related to the localization and density distribution of datasets were designed to assess the level of accessibility of the railway network managed by FGC and ZTM, focusing on:

¹⁵ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

¹⁶ See ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’.

- **Territorial data:** density distribution of urban fabric on land use (including continuous urban fabric, discontinuous dense urban fabric and isolated structures) and points of interest (e.g., commercial activities, schools, facilities, public services, attractions, etc.);
- **Socio-demographic data:** density distribution of total population, female population, elderly population and foreigner population¹⁷ per census section;
- **Mobility data:** density distribution of public transport services (e.g., metro and commuter railway stations, bus stops, tram stops, etc), road infrastructures and parking assets;
- **Railway network data:** metro and railway lines localization, tariff zones, characteristics of the railway infrastructures (under-ground or above-ground stations), characteristics of the territory surrounding the stations (city, town, village, countryside).

Raw data related to the urban scale were extracted on surrounding areas around each station within a **catchment area of 400 meter** (circular buffer area of 0.5 square kilometre), commonly known as comfortable walkable distance. **Data were post-processed** through:

1. Density-based calculation on buffer areas;
2. Normalization of values (z values in a range between 0 and 1);
3. Weighted formulas of normalized values to prioritize certain indicators.

The proposed approach allowed the calculation of territorial data index (TDI), socio-demographic data index (SDDI) and mobility data index (MDI). **Quintile frequency distribution of results** (see Annex 2) allowed the identification of positively relevant stations belonging to the highest quintile (≥ 80 th percentile) and negatively relevant stations belonging to the lowest quintile (≤ 20 th percentile).

The proposed approach for structured open data collection and analysis allowed the identification of a **short list of 20 heterogeneous and non-adjacent stations** (see Annex 2), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to the objectives of the Use Case I¹⁸.

Table 2 Structured open data analysis results related to the selected suitable stations managed by FGC.

FGC stations	TDI-Territorial Data Index	SDDI-Socio-demographic Data Index	MDI-Mobility Data Index
Sarrià	0,920	0,944	0,955
Pàdua	0,962	0,961	0,846
Pl. Espanya	0,883	0,856	0,991

¹⁷ Not available data for the Warsaw Metropolitan Area.

¹⁸ Further information are provided in 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

<i>Sant Cugat</i>	0,917	0,586	0,834
<i>Can Ros</i>	0,965	0,647	0,977
<i>Sant Joan</i>	0,065	0,163	0,388
<i>Igualada</i>	0,514	0,163	0,145
<i>El Palau</i>	0,071	0,164	0,107
<i>Martorell Enllac</i>	0,082	0,167	0,085
<i>Castellbell i el Vilar</i>	0,073	0,163	0,149

Table 3 Structured open data analysis results related to the selected suitable stations managed by ZTM.

ZTM stations	TDI-Territorial Data Index	SDDI-Socio-demographic Data Index	MDI-Mobility Data Index
<i>Warszawa Wilenska</i>	0,902	0,972	0,967
<i>Ratusz Arsenal</i>	0,760	0,943	0,976
<i>Zabki</i>	0,917	0,337	0,811
<i>Stoklosy</i>	0,490	0,927	0,870
<i>Plac Wilsona</i>	0,848	0,781	0,990
<i>Warszawa Pludy</i>	0,114	0,154	0,229
<i>Warszawa Zacisze - Wilno</i>	0,136	0,165	0,265
<i>Zalesie Gorne</i>	0,204	0,149	0,134
<i>Plochocin</i>	0,202	0,179	0,094
<i>Warszawa Wesola</i>	0,185	0,268	0,219

In order to further characterize the shortlisted stations, the research relied on the **Structured Proprietary Data** provided by FGC and ZTM (see Annex 2), focusing on:

- **Travel demand data:** number of passengers per station per year related to the entire metro and urban railway network;
- **Reliability of the service:** minutes of service delay per station, number of service disruption episodes, operational hours, frequency of the service;
- **Accessibility of the service:** discounted and flexible fares, pay-per-use payment options, subscription or monthly payment options;
- **Security of the transport infrastructures:** number and typology of incidents, presence and visibility of CCTV system, presence and visibility of SOS emergency phone, presence of police and security personnel.

The 20 metro and urban railway stations managed by FGC and ZTM, selected through structured open data analysis, were further investigated through: (i) structured proprietary data; (ii) onsite observations about universal design indicators; (iii) UESI questionnaires focused on women's needs and expectations; (iv) social media data from Twitter regarding the opinion of the end-users.

2.2.2 Observations (Use Case I)

Onsite non-participatory observations were aimed at further characterizing the metro and commuter urban railway stations previously selected through structured open data. Observations were based on an *ad hoc* designed checklist defined by SYS with the support of FGC and ZTM for the evaluation of relevant **infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics** related to women's needs in public transport infrastructure.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis¹⁹, the **assessment checklist**²⁰ was based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case I and it was composed of four main parts: (i) area surrounding the station; (ii) concourse level of the station; (iii) platform level of the station; (iv) carriage.

Data collection campaigns were executed on M15-January 2020 by the staff of FGC and ZTM at different time periods of the day (day and night) in order to mirror the various travel patterns of commuters. Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public moving around inside the stations and using facilities and recording their finding on paper. Results were organized in a tabular structure based on a collaborative Excel worksheet. In addition, some still photographs of the metro and urban railway stations was carried out.

¹⁹ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

²⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

Table 4 Observations data collection results related to the selected suitable stations managed by FGC.

FGC stations	No. Onsite Observations	Database Digitalization
<i>Sarrià</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Pàdua</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Pl. Espanya</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Sant Cugat</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Can Ros</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Sant Joan</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Igualada</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>El Palau</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Martorell Enllac</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Castellbell i el Vilar</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage

Table 5 Observations data collection results related to the selected suitable stations managed by ZTM.

ZTM stations	No. Onsite Observations	Database Digitalization
<i>Warszawa Wilenska</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Ratusz Arsenal</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Zabki</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Stoklosy</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Plac Wilsona</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Warszawa Pludy</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Warszawa Zacisze - Wilno</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage

Zalesie Gorne	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
Plochocin	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
Warszawa Wesola	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage

2.2.3 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case I)

UESI questionnaires were aimed at further characterizing the metro and commuter urban railway stations previously selected as described above. UESI questionnaires were based **on women’s needs and expectation** about the railway transport service and infrastructures.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis²¹, the outline of the UESI questionnaires²² was designed by TU Dublin based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case I and was composed of two main parts: (i) **users’ satisfaction** of the service and infrastructure design; (ii) **socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns** of the end-users which will allow us to present the findings in a disaggregated way regarding the many varieties of passengers.

UESI questionnaires were administered face to face by the staff of FGC and ZTM on the platform of the selected stations to ensure a wide range of participants at different time periods of the day, including peak and off-peak hours, from M16-February 2020 to M24-October 2020. The outline of the UESI questionnaire was translated from English into Spanish and Polish.

Table 6 UESI questionnaires data collection results related to the selected suitable stations managed by FGC.

FGC stations	No. UESI questionnaires	Database Digitalization
Sarrià	51	Questionnaire answers
Pàdua	70	Questionnaire answers
Pl. Espanya	41	Questionnaire answers
Sant Cugat	46	Questionnaire answers
Can Ros	58	Questionnaire answers
Sant Joan	55	Questionnaire answers

²¹ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

²² See ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’.

<i>Igualada</i>	35	Questionnaire answers
<i>El Palau</i>	9	Questionnaire answers
<i>Martorell Enllac</i>	66	Questionnaire answers
<i>Castellbell i el Vilar</i>	18	Questionnaire answers

Table 7 UESI questionnaires data collection results related to the selected suitable stations managed by ZTM.

ZTM stations	No. UESI questionnaires	Database Digitalization
<i>Warszawa Wilenska</i>	43	Questionnaire answers
<i>Ratusz Arsenal</i>	49	Questionnaire answers
<i>Zabki</i>	40	Questionnaire answers
<i>Stoklosy</i>	46	Questionnaire answers
<i>Plac Wilsona</i>	43	Questionnaire answers
<i>Warszawa Pludy</i>	55	Questionnaire answers
<i>Warszawa Zacisze - Wilno</i>	68	Questionnaire answers
<i>Zalesie Gorne</i>	40	Questionnaire answers
<i>Plochocin</i>	45	Questionnaire answers
<i>Warszawa Wesola</i>	43	Questionnaire answers

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected online from general public across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case I covers a **112% representativeness** considering the targeted objective of 800 questionnaires²³.

²³ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

2.2.4 Social Media Data (Use Case I)

The selected 10 stations were further characterized through the analysis of disaggregated **Social Media Data** collected from Twitter Social Network, focusing on: (i) geospatial data; (ii) time-based metadata; (iii) content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool²⁴ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M14-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) focusing on the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Social media data was aimed at monitoring the areas surrounding the selected relevant stations and **cluster geospatial data**. Then, the dataset was disaggregated based on the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference²⁵. This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and profile picture. This allowed us to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing **content analysis** through hashtags and relevant keywords.

Table 8 Social media data collection results related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Territorial Area of Reference	No. Tweets	Database Digitalization
Province of Barcelona (Spain)	20,000	Database creation
Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland)	25,000	Database creation

2.3 Users Perception Data (Use Case I)

2.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case I)

The goal of data collection through the online **DAD survey questionnaires** is to get the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the fairness characteristics (FCs) (level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level 2. The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires²⁶ was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through Thematic Analysis. The initial phase of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24).

The target for completed DAD questionnaires is approximately a minimum of 300 participants, (ideally 500) which will be gathered from general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy**: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media.

²⁴ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: *Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 392–399.

²⁵ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

²⁶ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated in English, Spanish, French, Italian, Polish and Serbian and data were collected according to the Communication plan (see D3.2 User engagement strategy) from across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

Due to all the DAD surveys are being collected through a digital survey (by internet), an Ex-post analysis about the quality of the questionnaires was conducted by EUT based on the percentage of completed and abandoned surveys. This analysis concluded that open questions are the main reason of the survey abandonment.

Table 9 DAD survey questionnaires data collection results related to the Use Case I.

Territorial Area of Reference	No. DAD Survey Questionnaires	Database Digitalization
France	95	Survey questionnaire answers
UK and Ireland	56	Survey questionnaire answers
Italy	12	Survey questionnaire answers
Poland	124	Survey questionnaire answers
Serbia	27	Survey questionnaire answers
Spain	67	Survey questionnaire answers

During the data collection, it was calculated the equivalent representativeness for the different profiles²⁷ with the probabilities for the characteristics of the PI as a monitoring tool. Figure 2 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data. Figure 2 shows the comparison between the collected data and the expected amount of data for the Use Case I (considering the collected 384 DAD Survey questionnaires as a reference). After the execution of the data collection campaigns, and according to the Grant Agreement, the number of DAD Survey Questionnaires targeted for the Use Case I are No. 500. Repeating the analysis by using this objective value, the comparison among the collected and targeted data for the Use Case I is presented in **Error! Reference source not found.**

²⁷ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

Figure 2 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Structured Data	To identify and characterise a short list of relevant metro and urban railway stations managed by FGC (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and ZTM (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland), where to perform further data collection activities.	Open data (territorial, socio-demographic, mobility data, etc.) and proprietary data (travel ridership, etc.).	M9-M17	SYS.	SYS.	FGC, SYS, ZTM.	-
Observations	To further characterize the selected metro and urban railway stations and to compare data with UESI questionnaires.	Assessment checklist: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M15	SYS.	SYS, FGC, ZTM.	FGC, ZTM.	-
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to investigate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the selected stations.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M16-M24	TU Dublin.	G&V, SYS, STIR, TU Dublin.	FGC, ZTM.	All Partner
Social Media Data	To characterize the selected stations through the opinion of the end-users by clustering Twitter data among space and time and by analysing hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: geospatial data, time-based meta data, hashtags and textual contents.	M14-M24	EURECAT.	EURECAT, SYS.	EURECAT.	-
DAD survey questionnaires	Weight and prioritize the FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs for the Use Case I.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC.	AITEC, EURECAT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.	-

Table 10 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case I.

3. Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car

3.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate women's **emotions as passengers of autonomous vehicles**. This is aimed at supporting the development of fully automated cars, able to dynamically adapt driving performance to women's preferences. The goal of Use Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology.

The **methodology for data collection**²⁸ for the Use Case II consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Observations based on an experimental investigation of gender driven emotional reactions to autonomous driving performance;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were focused on a sample of subjects participating in the experimental study managed by IBV-Instituto de Biomecánica (Valencia, Spain) (Observations and UESI questionnaires) and on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries. Users and Employees' Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries.

3.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case II)

3.2.1 Observations (Use Case II)

A series of **experiments in a simulator laboratory setting** were executed to collect data to objectively validate the impact of autonomous vehicles driving experience (Level 4 of automation) on **female passengers' emotional appraisal**²⁹, considering other relevant intersectional variables in transport.

A series of autonomous driving scenarios were designed considering different environmental, traffic and driving conditions (i.e., *independent variables*) to elicit emotional reactions to participants. The sample goal was obtaining a total of 40 participants³⁰, drivers between 25-55 years old, was an equilibrated experimental design in two main factors, gender and family composition involving care mobility duties, 10 men and 10 women with children under 12 years

²⁸ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

²⁹ Hohenberger, C., Spörrle, M., & Welp, I. M. (2016). How and why do men and women differ in their willingness to use automated cars? The influence of emotions across different age groups. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 94, 374-385.

³⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy'.

old and 10 men and 10 women without children under 12 years old (i.e., *between-subjects experimental design*). Additionally, sample age and technology affinity level were controlled within main factors to explore the effect and to avoid biases in *between-subjects* results.

The experimental procedure was based on the use of sensors to empirically monitor participants' psycho-physiological reactions (i.e., *dependent variables*). The main objective of the use of the physiological signals was to obtain a reliable estimation of the emotion of the participant based on the distinction between *Arousal* (emotion activation level) and *Valence* (qualitative connotation of the emotion) representation of emotional situation³¹. Several sensors for the recording of these signals have been included in the protocols:

- ECG sensor for obtaining the heart rate (HR) and the heart rate variability (HRV);
- A skin conductance sensor to record the Electro Dermal Activity (EDA);
- Two facial EMG sensors recording the muscle activity of *zygomaticus major* and *corrugator supercilia*.

Additionally, during the experiments, the participant face was recorded in video to facilitate emotion identification associated with facial expression by means of visualization or automatic identification by a specific software.

The experimental protocol was defined by IBV³², with support from AITEC, SYS and TU Dublin. Data were collected by the staff of IBV through experimental campaign execution from M23-September 2020 to M24-October 2020.

To reach the goal a total of 56 sessions (2h of duration each), the experimental procedure was carried in IBV facilities with the participation of 28 women and 28 men. In case of No.11 sessions participant felt sick (among which 5 men and 6 women), due to de immersive dynamic driving simulation and No.5 session had problem with the signal acquisition and were discarded (3 men and 2 women). Those sessions were repeated until the equilibrated sample of 40 subjects was obtained.

The main goal of the designed experimental protocol was the examination of the **gender-driven identification of stressors related to autonomous driving performance**, focusing on the FCs identified through Thematic Analysis³³.

3.2.2 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case II)

UESI questionnaires were focused on the satisfaction of the end-users related to autonomous vehicles. The outline of UESI questionnaires was composed by two main parts. The first is focused on profiling the **socio-demographic characteristics** and **mobility patterns** of the end-users and was administrated before the execution of the experiments. The second part was focused on evaluating the **users' satisfaction regarding the autonomous driving performance** experienced through the simulator.

³¹ Lang, Peter J., Margaret M. Bradley, and Bruce N. Cuthbert. 1999. 'International Affective Picture System (IAPS): Instruction Manual and Affective Ratings'. The Center for Research in Psychophysiology, University of Florida.

³² See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

³³ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

The outline of UESI questionnaires was defined by IBV³⁴ considering the CFCs, FCs and influencing parameters identified through the Thematic Analysis³⁵. UESI questionnaires were administrated by the staff of IBV from M23-September 2020 to M24-October 2020 to participants of the experimental study. A total of 50 UESI questionnaires were collected 50 during the experimental sessions , 23 men and 27 women.

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in English and data were collected online from the general public across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case II covers a **230% representativeness** considering the targeted objective of 40 questionnaires³⁶.

Table 11 UESI questionnaires data collection results related to use case II simulations.

Territorial Area of Reference	No. UESI questionnaires	Database Digitalization
Valencia, Spain (administered during IBV experiments)	50	Questionnaire answers
Online version	42	Questionnaire answers

3.2.3 Social Media Data (Use Case II)

A series of disaggregated social media data were collected from **Twitter Social Network**, focusing on their content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool³⁷ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M12-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** (about 1 Million of Tweets in total).

The dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference³⁸. This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and profile picture. This allowed to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing **content analysis** through hashtags and relevant keywords.

³⁴ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

³⁵ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

³⁶ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

³⁷ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: *Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 392–399.

³⁸ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

3.3 Users and Employees' Perception Data (Use Case II)

3.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case II)

The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires is to get the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the fairness characteristics (FCs) (Level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level 2. The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires³⁹ was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis.

The initial phase of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24). It is anticipated that the online DAD will provide approximately 300 responses to the questionnaire's respondents⁴⁰ (a minimum of 300 participants and ideally 500) gathered from the general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy**: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated in English, Spanish, French, Italian, Polish and Serbian languages and data were collected via the online platform of DAD, following the Communication plan defined in D3.2 User engagement strategy, from across partner countries in UK, Ireland, Spain, France, Italy, Poland and Serbia in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

Due to all the DAD surveys are being collected through a digital survey (by internet), an Ex-post analysis about the quality of the questionnaires was conducted by EURECAT based on the % of completed and abandoned surveys. This analysis concluded that open questions are the main reason of the survey abandonment.

Table 12 DAD survey questionnaires data collection results related to the Use Case II.

Territorial Area of Reference	No. DAD Survey Questionnaires	Database Digitalization
France	16	Done
UK and Ireland	22	Done
Italy	4	Done

³⁹ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

⁴⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy'.

Poland	32	Done
Serbia	12	Done
Spain	30	Done

During the data collection, it was calculated the equivalent representativeness for the different profiles⁴¹ with the probabilities for the characteristics of the PI as a monitoring tool. Figure 3 shows the comparison between the collected data and the expected amount of data for the UCI (considering the collected 116 DAD Survey Questionnaires as a reference). After the execution of the data collection campaigns, and according to the Grant Agreement, the number of DAD Survey Questionnaires targeted for the Use Case II are No. 500. Repeating the analysis by using this objective value, the comparison among the collected and targeted data for the Use Case II is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data.

⁴¹ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Observations	To identify stress triggers related to autonomous driving performance, focusing on gender.	Experiments in a driving simulator laboratory setting.	M23-M24	IBV.	IBV.	IBV.	AITEC, SYS, TU Dublin.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the autonomous driving performance experienced through the simulator.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M23-M24	TU Dublin.	IBV.	IBV (in observations).	All Partner.
Social Media Data	To analyse hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: hashtags and textual contents.	M14-M24	EURECAT.	EURECAT.	EURECAT.	IBV.
DAD survey questionnaires	Weight and prioritize the FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs for the Use Case II.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC.	All Partner.	-

Table 13 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case II.

4. Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management

4.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case III is to investigate the **women's needs as users of bike sharing services**. This is aimed at supporting the development of policies for gender-equitable bike sharing fleet management. The goal of the Use Case III is to increase the percentage of women using bike sharing services.

The methodology for **data collection**⁴² for the Use Case III consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Structured data regarding the bike sharing docking stations and the operation of the service;
 - Observations regarding universal design indicators of bike sharing docking stations and their surrounding urban context;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were collected focusing on the bike sharing docking stations managed by **VELIB (Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib' Métropole)** (Metropolitan Area of Paris, France). Users and Employees' Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several **European Countries**.

4.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case III)

4.2.1 Structured Data (Use Case III)

Structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M18-April 2019) was utilised in order to select and characterise a sample of suitable 20 bike sharing docking stations managed by **VELIB** (who manage 1377 docking stations in total).

Structured Open Data were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open data repositories, national geoportals and census databases (see Annex 3). Preliminary structured open data analysis was based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS). A series of thematic maps⁴³ related to the localization and density distribution of datasets were designed to assess the level of accessibility of the bike sharing docking stations managed by **VELIB**, focusing on:

⁴² See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁴³ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

- **Territorial data:** density distribution of urban fabric on land use (including continuous urban fabric, discontinuous dense urban fabric and isolated structures) and points of interest (e.g., commercial activities, schools, facilities, public services, attractions, etc.);
- **Socio-demographic data:** density distribution of total population, female population, elderly population and foreigner population per census section;
- **Mobility data:** density distribution of public transport services (e.g., metro and commuter railway stations, bus stops, tram stops, etc) and cycleway infrastructures;
- **Bike sharing docking stations network data:** docking stations capacity (number of bikes available for each docking station).

Raw data related to the urban scale were extracted on surrounding census section around each docking station. **Data were post-processed** through:

1. Density-based calculation on buffer areas;
2. Normalization of values (z values in a range between 0 and 1);
3. Weighted formulas of normalized values to prioritize certain indicators.

The proposed approach allowed the calculation of territorial data index (TDI), socio-demographic data index (SDDI) and mobility data index (MDI). **Quintile frequency distribution of results** (see Annex 3) allowed the identification of positively relevant stations belonging to the highest quintile (≥ 80 th percentile) and negatively relevant stations belonging to the lowest quintile (≤ 20 th percentile).

The proposed approach for structured open data collection and analysis allowed the identification of a **short list of 20 heterogeneous and non-adjacent docking stations** (see Annex 3), characterized by positively and negatively relevant fairness characteristics identified in the thematic analysis conducted for Use Case III⁴⁴.

Table 14 Structured open data analysis results related to the selected suitable docking stations managed by VELIB.

VELIB docking stations	TDI-Territorial Data Index	SDDI-Socio-demographic Data Index	MDI-Mobility Data Index
Versailles - Claude Terrasse	0,824	0,972	0,931
Square RenéViviani - Montebello	0,849	0,950	0,952
Godot de Mauroy - Madeleine	0,940	0,906	0,872
Charenton - Place du Col Bourgoin	0,956	0,986	0,930
Boyer-Barret - Raymond Losserand	0,839	0,868	0,954

⁴⁴ Further information about Structure Open Data analysis are provided in 'Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description'.

<i>Cité Riverin - Château d'Eau</i>	0,927	0,986	0,989
<i>Faubourg Poissonnière - Delta</i>	0,932	0,987	0,985
<i>Halles - Bourdonnais</i>	0,957	0,974	0,992
<i>Guy Môquet - Saint-Ouen</i>	0,859	0,952	0,938
<i>Mathis - Flandre</i>	0,926	0,933	0,883
<i>Sorbonne - Ecoles</i>	0,039	0,070	0,089
<i>Mahatma Gandhi</i>	0,115	0,167	0,110
<i>Sérurier - Alphonse Aulard</i>	0,115	0,178	0,096
<i>Louis Pasteur - Albert Petit</i>	0,028	0,070	0,119
<i>Clichy - Douai</i>	0,032	0,093	0,163
<i>Château de Vincennes</i>	0,034	0,102	0,111
<i>Gare de Lyon - Van Gogh</i>	0,062	0,095	0,115
<i>Porte de la Plaine</i>	0,151	0,166	0,115
<i>Gare RER les Grésillons</i>	0,118	0,126	0,081
<i>Rond-Point Rhin et Danube</i>	0,111	0,140	0,109

In order to further characterize the shortlisted stations, structured open data were merged with the **Structured Proprietary Data** provided by VELIB (Annex 3), focusing on:

- **Travel demand data:** number of users per docking station per year, number of users per docking station per month, origin/destination matrix of the users, average length of trips, average time duration of trips;
- **Accessibility and Spontaneity:** number of public campaigns on cycling in the past year, number of adverts on bike-sharing services in the past year, type of requirement for signing-up for membership, number and percentage of cash payment members, the entry cost of bike-sharing scheme (upfront cost), rental charges above one hour, annual membership cost of the scheme, types of safety gear supplied by operator, nature and type of insurance cover for bikes and users (i.e. damages, theft, accidents etc.) if available, number and percentage of docking stations at transport hubs, number and percentage of transport hubs with docking stations, number and percentage of low-income and

minority neighbourhoods with docking stations, number and percentage of docking stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods, number and Percentage of Bike-sharing stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods, number and percentage of bikes with a child seat, trailers and carriages for carrying children and goods, number of practical cycling programs/training held in the past year, number and percentage of docking stations with shelter, number and percentage of docking stations with toilet facilities;

- **Safety and Security:** percentage of bike network segregated from vehicular traffic, number of cycling training programmes organised in a year to educate cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road, number of public campaigns held to address harassment of cyclist in the past one year, number of public campaigns held to boost cyclists' confidence in the past one year, number and percentage of docking stations with security devices, number and percentage of docking stations with CCTV, number and percentage of bikes with well-functioning brakes, lights and reflectors etc, number and percentage of docking stations with information centres for users, speed limits on roads with cycle lanes, percentage of roads with physically separated bike lanes from vehicular traffic;
- **Social Constraints:** number of campaigns targeted at low-income and minority groups/neighbourhoods to promote cycling as an acceptable form of transport, number of practical cycling training programmes;
- **Weather and Topography:** percentage of cycle network that is all-weather cycle friendly, number and percentage of electric bikes among bike fleet and at each docking station.

The proposed approach for structured open data collection allowed the identification of a **short list of 20 heterogeneous and non-adjacent docking stations** (see Annex 3), characterized by positively and negatively relevant fairness characteristics related to the objectives of the Use Case III⁴⁵. The shortlisted docking stations were further investigated through: (i) structured proprietary data; (ii) onsite observations about universal design indicators; (iii) UESI questionnaires focused on women's needs and expectations; (iv) social media data from Twitter regarding the opinion of the end-users.

4.2.2 Observations (Use Case III)

Onsite observations were aimed at further characterizing the bike sharing docking stations previously selected through structured open data. Observations were based on a checklist designed by ENU with the support of SYS which used the findings collected from the thematic analysis to evaluate the relevant **infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics** related to the women's needs as users of bike sharing docking stations.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis⁴⁶, the **assessment checklist**⁴⁷ was based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case III which included five main concepts: (i)

⁴⁵ Further information about Structure Open Data analysis are provided in 'Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description'.

⁴⁶ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁴⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

Accessibility and Spontaneity; (ii) Safety and Security; (iii) Social Constraints; (iv) Weather and Topography; (v) Other.

Data collection campaigns were executed from M17-March 2020 to M24-October 2020 by the staff of G&V at different time periods of the day (day and night). Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public and recording their finding on paper. Results were organized in a tabular structure based on a collaborative Excel worksheet. In addition, some still photo survey of the metro and urban railway stations was carried out.

Table 15 Observations data collection results related to the selected suitable docking stations managed by VELIB.

VELIB docking stations	No. Onsite Observations	Database Digitalization
<i>Versailles - Claude Terrasse</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Square René Viviani - Montebello</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Godot de Mauroy - Madeleine</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Charenton - Place du Col Bourgoin</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Boyer-Barret - Raymond Losserand</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Cité Riverin - Château d'Eau</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Faubourg Poissonnière - Delta</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Halles - Bourdonnais</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Guy Môquet - Saint-Ouen</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Mathis - Flandre</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Sorbonne - Ecoles</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Mahatma Gandhi</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Séururier - Alphonse Aulard</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Louis Pasteur - Albert Petit</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Clichy - Douai</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Château de Vincennes</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
<i>Gare de Lyon - Van Gogh</i>	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage

Porte de la Plaine	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
Gare RER les Grésillons	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage
Rond-Point Rhin et Danube	2 at different time periods of the day (day and night)	Observation checklist and file footage

4.2.3 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case III)

UESI questionnaires were aimed at further characterizing the bike sharing docking stations previously selected through structured open data. UESI questionnaires were based on a **questionnaire designed to provide data related to the women’s needs and expectations regarding** bike sharing services and infrastructures.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis⁴⁸, the outline of the UESI questionnaires⁴⁹ was designed by TU Dublin based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case III such as cost, safety equipment and local cycling infrastructure and was composed of two main parts: (i) **users’ satisfaction** of the service and infrastructure design; (ii) **socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns** of the end-users which allows us to provide disaggregated data on women users

UESI questionnaires were administrated face to face by VELIB from M17-March 2020 to M24-October 2020. They will be held as soon as the sanitary crisis allows people to go back on the street, at the selected docking stations at different time periods of the day, including peak and off-peak hours.

Table 16 Observations data collection results related to the selected suitable docking stations managed by VELIB.

VELIB docking stations	No. UESI questionnaires	Database Digitalization
Versailles - Claude Terrasse	22	Questionnaire answers
Square René Viviani - Montebello	17	Questionnaire answers
Godot de Mauroy - Madeleine	15	Questionnaire answers
Charenton - Place du Colonel Bourgoin	21	Questionnaire answers
Boyer-Barret - Raymond Losserand	21	Questionnaire answers
Cité Riverin - Château d'Eau	21	Questionnaire answers

⁴⁸ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

⁴⁹ See ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’.

<i>Faubourg Poissonnière - Delta</i>	21	Questionnaire answers
<i>Halles - Bourdonnais</i>	12	Questionnaire answers
<i>Guy Môquet - Saint-Ouen</i>	22	Questionnaire answers
<i>Mathis - Flandre</i>	21	Questionnaire answers
<i>Sorbonne - Ecoles</i>	26	Questionnaire answers
<i>Mahatma Gandhi</i>	21	Questionnaire answers
<i>Sérurier - Alphonse Aulard</i>	24	Questionnaire answers
<i>Louis Pasteur - Albert Petit</i>	20	Questionnaire answers
<i>Clichy - Douai</i>	24	Questionnaire answers
<i>Château de Vincennes</i>	17	Questionnaire answers
<i>Gare de Lyon - Van Gogh</i>	22	Questionnaire answers
<i>Porte de la Plaine</i>	15	Questionnaire answers
<i>Gare RER les Grésillons</i>	8	Questionnaire answers
<i>Rond-Point Rhin et Danube</i>	22	Questionnaire answers

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in languages and data were collected online from the general public across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case III covers a **99% representativeness** considering the targeted objective of 400 questionnaires⁵⁰.

4.2.4 Social Media Data (Use Case III)

The selected docking stations were further characterized through the analysis of disaggregated social media data collected from **Twitter Social Network**, focusing on: (i) geospatial data; (ii) time-based metadata; (iii) content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool⁵¹ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M14-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) focusing on the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

⁵⁰ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

⁵¹ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: *Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 392–399.

This was aimed at monitoring the areas surrounding the selected relevant docking stations and **cluster geospatial data**. Then, the dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference⁵². This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and profile picture. This allowed to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing **content analysis** through hashtags and relevant keywords.

Table 17 Social media data collection results related to the Paris Region (France).

Territorial Area of Reference	No. Tweets	Database Digitalization
Paris Region (France)	40,000	Database creation

4.3 Users and Employees' Perception Data (Use Case III)

4.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case III)

The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires is to get the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the fairness characteristics (FCs) (level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level2.

The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires⁵³ was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through Thematic Analysis. The initial phase of data collection using the DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M18). It is anticipated the DAD survey will result in approximately 300 completed responses gathered from members of the general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy** such as an innovative snowball approach for complex surveys, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated into English, Spanish, French, Italian, Polish and Serbian and data were collected according the communication plan described in D3.2 User engagement strategy from across all partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

Due to all the DAD surveys are being collected through a digital survey (by internet), an Ex-post analysis about the quality of the questionnaires was conducted by EUT based on the % of completed and abandoned surveys. This analysis concluded that open questions are the main reason of the survey abandonment.

⁵² Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

⁵³ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

Table 18 DAD survey questionnaires data collection results related to the Use Case III.

Territorial Area of Reference	No. DAD Survey Questionnaires	Database Digitalization
France	17	Done
UK and Ireland	22	Done
Italy	3	Done
Poland	31	Done
Serbia	6	Done
Spain	16	Done

During the data collection, it was calculated the equivalent representativeness for the different profiles⁵⁴ with the probabilities for the characteristics of the PI as a monitoring tool. Figure 2 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data. Figure 4 shows the comparison between the collected and the expected amount of data for the Use Case III (considering the collected 97 DAD Survey questionnaires as a reference). After the execution of the data collection campaigns, and according to the Grant Agreement, the number of DAD Survey Questionnaires targeted for the Use Case III are No. 500. Repeating the analysis by using this objective value, the comparison among the collected and targeted data for the Use Case III is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data.

⁵⁴ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Structured Data	To identify a short list of relevant bike sharing pickup/return points managed by VELIB within the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France), where to perform future data collection activities.	Open data (territorial, socio-demographic, mobility data, travel demand data) and proprietary data (e.g., travel ridership).	M9-M17	SYS.	SYS.	SYS, VELIB.	-
Observations	To further characterize the selected bike sharing pickup/return points and to compare data with UESI questionnaires.	Assessment checklist: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24	SYS.	ENU, SYS.	G&V	-
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the bike sharing pickup/return points.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24	TU Dublin.	G&V, TU Dublin.	VELIB.	All Partner.
Social Media Data	To characterize the selected pickup/return points through the opinion of the end-users by clustering Twitter data among space and time and by analysing hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: geospatial data, time-based meta data, hashtag and text content.	M14-M24	EURECAT.	EURECAT, SYS.	EURECAT.	-
DAD survey questionnaires	Weigh and prioritize the FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs for the Use Case III.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC.	All Partner.	-

Table 19 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case III.

5. Use Case IV: Women Recruitment in Railways and Freight / CSR Protocols

5.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case IV is to investigate the **women's needs as employees in transport sector**. The goal of the Use Case IV is to assess the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment in different positions and roles in the transport sector and help to increase the percentage of women working on-site and off-site in specific male dominated roles in railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors.

The **methodology for data collection**⁵⁵ for Use Case IV consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Structured data: regarding percentage of women involved in professional jobs related to transport sector in several EU Countries. In different job roles, data regarding their career progressions, their job opportunity and training, conditions of employment etc.
 - UESI questionnaires: regarding the opinion of the employees;
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.
 - Semi-structured online Interviews with employees

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Employers Provision Data in this case) were provided by the Human Resources Department of **FGC-Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya** (Province of Barcelona, Spain), **RINA-Rina Services spa** (Genoa, Italy) and **ZTM-Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa** (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland). Users and Employees' Perception Data (only Employees Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the women involved in professional jobs related to transport sector across several **European Countries** (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain and UK)

Additionally, semi-structured online interviews with employees were seen as necessary in the mid-term of the DIAMOND's project for the use case IV to gather deeper data for the interdisciplinary analysis especially for specific profiles.

5.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case IV)

5.2.1 Structured Data (Use Case IV)

Structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020) is aimed at characterizing the level of participation of women to on-site and off-site professional jobs related to transport sector (railway, freight transport and logistics sectors). On-site professional jobs are defined as those related to administrative and office management support in transport departments, operators for warehouses rail and maintenance technicians etc. Off-site professional jobs are defined as those including drivers of short and long distances.

⁵⁵ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Structured Open Data collection was performed by STIR and TU Dublin using historical series of open data collected from Euro Stats which included data from across several European Countries (see Annex 4) and through **Structured Proprietary Data provided by partners at FGC, RINA and ZTM.**

The goal of structured data collection was to depict the current level of participation of women in the wider transport sector and were collected considering the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified through Thematic Analysis⁵⁶, based on level I CFC's of job characteristics, personal circumstances, individual characteristics and socio-economic conditions.

5.2.2 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case IV)

UESI questionnaires were designed and developed in a similar manner using the level I CFC's as discussed above in order to highlight the barriers and needs related to the **participation of women to professional jobs related to transport sector** in EU, focusing on focusing the Human Resources Departments of FGC and ZTM.

The outline of UESI questionnaires⁵⁷ was composed in two main parts. The first is focused on profiling the **socio-demographic characteristics** and **career profiles** of participants employees in transport sector and the second part is focused on evaluating **employees' satisfaction** regarding job conditions and employability.

The outline of UESI questionnaires was defined by G&V, STIR and TU Dublin (in alphabetic order) considering the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified through Thematic Analysis⁵⁸. UESI questionnaires were collected by TU Dublin from M17-March 2020 to M24-October 2020.

Table 20 UESI questionnaires data collection results related to the Human Resources Departments of FGC and ZTM.

Human Resource Departments	No. UESI questionnaires	Database Digitalization
FGC	90	Questionnaire answers
ZTM	140	Questionnaire answers

Then, then outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected online from general public across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs. The number of UESI questionnaires gathered through data collection activities for the Use Case III covers a **38% representativeness** considering the targeted objective of 600 questionnaires⁵⁹.

⁵⁶ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁵⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

⁵⁸ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁵⁹ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

5.3 Users and Employees' Perception Data (Use Case IV)

5.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case IV)

The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires is to get the opinion of end-users in order to weight/prioritize, by using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), the fairness characteristics (FCs) (level 2) identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of FCs level 1 and FCs level2.

The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires⁶⁰ was defined by AITEC, with the initial phase of data collection performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24). The questionnaires were filled by a large sample of respondents⁶¹ (according to the DoA, the DIAMOND project should collect a minimum of 300 surveys and ideally 500) gathered from general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy** such as an innovative snowball approach specially designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated into Spanish, French, Polish, Italian, Polish and Serbia and data were collected according to the communication plan (see D3.2 User engagement strategy) from across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), STIR (UK), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

Due to all the DAD surveys are being collected through a digital survey (by internet), an Ex-post analysis about the quality of the questionnaires was conducted by EUT based on the % of completed and abandoned surveys. This analysis concluded that open questions are the main reason of the survey abandonment.

Table 21 DAD survey questionnaires data collection results related to the Use Case IV.

Territorial Area of Reference	No. DAD Survey Questionnaires	Database Digitalization
France	17	Done
UK and Ireland	19	Done
Italy	1	Done
Poland	36	Done
Serbia	6	Done
Spain	21	Done

⁶⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

⁶¹ See 'Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy'.

During the data collection, it was calculated the equivalent representativeness for the different profiles⁶² with the probabilities for the characteristics of the PI as a monitoring tool. Figure 2 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data. Figure 5 shows the comparison between the collected and the expected amount of data for the Use Case IV (considering the collected 100 DAD Survey questionnaires as a reference). After the execution of the data collection campaigns, and according to the Grant Agreement, the number of DAD Survey Questionnaires targeted for the Use Case IV are No. 500. Repeating the analysis by using this objective value, the comparison among the collected and targeted data for the Use Case IV is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Comparison between collected, expected and targeted data.

⁶² See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Structured Data	To define the level of participation of women to on-site and off-site professional jobs related to transport sector in several European Countries.	Open data and proprietary data.	M9-M25	TU Dublin.	STIR, TU Dublin.	FGC, STIR, TU Dublin ZTM.	AITEC, EURECAT.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and career profiles of the employees and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the job conditions.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, career profiles, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24	TU Dublin.	G&V, STIR, TU Dublin.	FGC, ZTM.	All Partner.
DAD survey questionnaires	Weigh and prioritize the FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis and clustered in a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs for the Use Case IV.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC.	All Partner.	-

Table 22 Description of Service and Employers' Provision Data and Users and Employees' Perception Data for the Use Case IV.

6. Conclusion

The current document ‘Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description’ describes the **data collection activities** executed within the ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’ of the DIAMOND project (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020). In this regard, the document includes information regarding the identification of **dataset sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and the partners of the Consortium responsible for each data collection activity.**

The main objective of DIAMOND project is to turn data into reliable and actionable knowledge for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees. The document is focused on the four **Use Cases of the DIAMOND project** (see Table 23 for the summary and timeline):

- Use Case I - Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Use Case	Data Typology	Data collection timeline
Use Case I	Structured Data, Observations, UESI questionnaires, Social Media, DAD survey.	M9-M24
Use Case II	Observations, UESI questionnaires, Social Media, DAD survey.	M10-M24
Use Case III	Structured Data, Observations, UESI questionnaires, Social Media, DAD survey.	M14-M24
Use Case IV	Structured Data, UESI questionnaires, DAD survey.	M9-M25

Table 23 Data collection campaigns summary.

Annex I – Datasets related to Thematic Analysis

Literature review datasets

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Literature review results

Literature Review Use Case I	ID			CFCs				FCs							
	V1 - L3 Public transport	V4 - L1 New technologies	V4 - L2 New business models	Accessibility of the Service	Design of the Infrastructure	Safety & Security	Service Availability & Efficiency	Travel & Wayfinding Information	Ticketing Options & Fares	Travel Purpose	Universal Design	Cleanliness & Maintenance	Furniture & Facilities	Harassment & Pickpocketing	Overcrowding & Emergency Situations
(Albeniz & Alonso, 2009)	•			•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	
(APTA, 2013)	•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	
(Asian Development Bank, 2013)	•			•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Duchène, 2011)	•			•	•	•	•		•	•	•		•	•	
(European Commission, 1994)	•			•	•	•	•		•		•		•	•	
(FIA Foundation, 2017)	•			•	•	•	•	•			•		•	•	•
(Gheorghiu et al., 2017)		•	•	•		•		•	•					•	
(Madriaza et al., 2016)	•				•	•					•		•	•	•
(ITF, 2018)	•				•	•					•		•	•	•
(Loukaitou-Sideris, 2014)	•				•	•					•	•	•	•	
(MacLeod et al., 2006)	•		•	•			•	•	•		•				
(Network Rail, 2011)	•			•	•	•	•	•	•		•		•	•	•
(Peters, 2013)	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•
(Shrestha et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	
(Soltani, Sham, Awang, & Yaman, 2012)	•			•				•	•		•		•		
(Suman & Bolia, 2019)	•			•	•	•	•		•		•	•	•	•	•
(Thompson et al., 2012)	•			•	•	•	•	•			•	•	•	•	•
(Transport for London, 2012)	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•
(Transport for London, 2015)	•			•	•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•
(Turner, 2012)	•			•	•	•	•		•		•		•	•	•

Figure 6 Results of literature review for the Use Case I.

Literature review Use Case II	ID		CFCs						FCs																			
	V2 - L2 Vehicle today	V5 - L1 Vehicle tomorrow	Safety & Security	Comfort	Mobility	Economy	Environment	Design options	Accident rate	Human errors	Training	Traffic management	Trust in technology	Simultaneity	Traffic efficiency	Travel time	Congestion	Accessibility	Monetary costs	Non-monetary costs	Vehicle efficiency	Noise	Emissions	Public health	Infrastructure adaptation	Vehicle shape	Vehicle behaviour	Human Machine Interface (HMI)
(Barnard et al., 2018)	•	•	•		•	•	•								•				•	•				•				
(Blokpoel & Lu, 2018)		•	•		•	•									•						•							
(Böhm et al., 2017)	•	•		•									•															
(Brell, Philipsen, & Ziefle, 2019)	•		•	•	•	•	•						•				•				•		•					
(Collet & Musicant, 2019)	•	•	•																									
(Diels et al., 2017)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•		•					•								
(Duy Son et al., 2018)	•		•		•	•		•									•			•								•
(Hand & Lee, 2018)	•	•		•									•															
(Hohenberger, Spörrle & Welpel, 2016)	•	•	•	•	•		•			•			•					•					•	•				
(Jugade et al. 2018)	•	•	•					•	•																•		•	•
(Kuhn et al., 2018)	•	•	•		•			•				•		•											•			•
(Kyriakidis, Happee & De Winter, 2015)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•	•		•			•					•	•	•		
(Meschtscherjakov et al., 2018)	•		•	•				•	•	•	•		•															•
(Nielsen & Christiansen, 2018)	•		•	•	•								•					•										
(Olsen & Sweet, 2019)	•	•	•	•	•				•				•	•	•													
(Patz, 2018)	•	•	•		•		•							•														
(Pereira, Costa, Costa, & Arezes, 2019)	•		•	•				•		•			•															•
(Peter & Pernilla, 2018)	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•							•	•			•	•		•	•		•		
(Pettigrew et al., 2019)	•	•	•	•	•			•		•			•					•										
(Raposo et al., 2018)	•	•	•			•	•		•			•							•				•	•				
(Rogic et al., 2018)	•							•																				•
(Schieben et al., 2019)	•							•																				
(Schwarz, Gaspar, & Brown, 2019)	•			•																								
(Shergold, Wilson & Parkhurst, 2016)	•	•	•	•	•				•				•					•										

Figure 7 Results of literature review for the Use Case II.

Literature review Use Case III	ID			CFCs							FCs																	
	V1 - L3 Public transport	V4 - L1 New technologies	V4 - L2 New business models	Accessibility & spontaneity	Safety & Security	Social constraints	Weather & Topography	Public awareness	Sign-up & booking process	Membership cost	Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	Proximity of docking station	Helmet issues	Travelling with children/Carrying things	Travel distance	Insufficient Infrastructure	Driver behaviour	Separate Infrastructure	Personal safety	Harassment	Safe environment	Confidence/ experience	Traffic safety	Subjective norm	Socio-cultural constrain	Family responsibilities	Weather	Topography
(Berger, Reback, & Palmatier, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•																
(Bikeplus, 2017)		•		•	•	•	•		•		•				•								•					•
(Bonham & Wilson, 2012)	•		•	•	•	•	•							•	•	•	•						•	•	•	•	•	•
(Bopp, Child, & Campbell, 2014)	•			•	•	•	•		•					•	•	•		•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Campbell et al., 2016)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•			•	•						•					•	
(Clark & Curl, 2016)		•	•	•	•	•		•		•									•									
(Cornish Jones, 2015)	•		•	•	•	•	•					•		•		•				•		•			•	•		
(Duncan et al., 2016)	•	•	•	•	•	•		•				•			•			•			•							
(Faghih-Imani et al., 2014)	•		•	•	•	•	•							•	•												•	
(Fishman et al., 2014)	•		•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•				•							•					
(Fishman et al., 2015)	•		•	•	•	•						•			•				•									
(Fishman, Washington, & Haworth, 2012)	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•		•				•				•	•
(Howland et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•		•		•					•				•				•		•			
(Jin, Kong, Wu, & Sui, 2018)	•			•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•							•									
(Mateo-Babiano et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•			•	•		•			•		•		•	•		
(McNeil et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•			•	•			•	•	•	•			•	•		•	•	•				
(McNeil et al., 2017a)	•		•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•		•	•	•	•			
(McNeil et al., 2017b)	•		•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•		•	•	•	•	•		
(McNeil, Broach, & Dill, 2018)	•		•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•										•			
(Médard de Chardon, Caruso, & Thomas, 2017)	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•		•									•	•
(Murphy & Usher, 2015)	•			•	•	•		•					•		•	•							•	•				
(Stredwick, 2017)	•			•	•	•		•					•		•			•	•	•	•	•	•			•		
(Transport for London, 2011)	•			•	•	•	•	•		•					•				•		•		•		•	•	•	•
(Zanotto, 2014)	•		•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•		•			•			•		•		•	•	•	•

Figure 8 Results of literature review for the Use Case III.

Literature review Use Case IV	ID	CFCs						FCs																		
	V3 Job Holders Today	V6 Job Holders Tomorrow	Socio-economic Conditions	Job Characteristics	Personal Circumstances	Individual Characteristics	Job Segregation	Policy/Legal	Demand Factors	Female facilities	Terms and Conditions	HR Policies	Negative attitude of male colleagues	Safety and security	Training Provision	Flexible Working	Caring/parenting responsibilities	Economic Deprivation	Residential Location/Distance from Employment	Access to/ownership off resources	Health Status and Wellbeing	Adaptability - attitudes to work and travel to work	Demographic	Skills	Educational level/attainment	
(Anciaes, 2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•	•	•	•	
(Azad Foundation & University of Western Ontario, 2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•		•	•		•				•	•			•	•
(Batac et al., 2012)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•	•	•									
(Colgan, Johnstone, & Shaw, 1996)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•	•	•					•			•	•
(Corral & Isusi, 2007)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•	•	•								•	•
(Duchène, 2011)	•	•	•	•	•		•			•	•		•	•	•	•	•									
(European Commission, 2011)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•				•
(European Commission, 2017)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•						•		•	•
(European Commission, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•								•	•
(French & Strachan, 2009)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•		•	•	•					•	•		•	•
(Giannelos et al., 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•						•	•			
(Hanlon, 1996)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•		•	•	•		•	•	•								•	
(ILO International Labour Office, 2010)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•	•		•	•			•	•	•	•	•
(International Transport Workers, 2008)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•									
(Keinert-Kisin, 2016)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Kurshitashvili & Isik, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•			•	•
(Kurshitashvili, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•					•			•	
(McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•		•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Sicard, 2012)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•		•	•	•	•	•	•					•	•		•	
(Tanis, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•					•	•		•	•
(Turnbull, 2013)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Women in Rail, 2015)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•					•	•	•	•	•
International Transport Workers Federation (2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•									

Figure 9 Results of literature review for the Use Case IV.

Annex 2 – Datasets related to Use Case I

Structured Open and Proprietary Data (Use Case I)

Table 24 The list of retrieved structured open data and structured proprietary data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant metro and urban railway infrastructures managed by FGC.

Data	Data typology	Indicators	Data Source	Year
Structured Open Data	Preliminary Data	Boundaries of the Province of Barcelona	Cartographic Institute of Catalunya	2019
		Boundaries of the census section of the region of Catalunya	National Statistics Institute	2019
		Localization of the FGC metro and commuter railway stations	Barcelona's City Hall Data Service	2019
	Territorial Data	Localization of urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
		Localization of points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Socio-demographic Data	Total population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Age of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Gender of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011

	Mobility Data	Nationality of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011	
		Localization of public transport services	OpenStreetMap	2019	
		Localization of road infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019	
		Localization of parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019	
	Railway Network Data	Localization of FGC lines	FGC	2019	
		Localization of FGC tariff zones	FGC	2019	
		Infrastructure characteristics of the stations (i.e. underground or above ground)	FGC	2019	
		Characteristics of the territory surrounding the stations (city, town, village, countryside)	FGC	2019	
	Structured Proprietary Data	Travel Demand Data	Number of passengers per stations per year	FGC	2017-2018
			Number of passengers per stations per month	FGC	2017-2018
Reliability of the service		Percentage of trains on time (no delays or delays of less than 3 minutes)	FGC	2019	

		Operational hours and frequency of the service	FGC	2019
	Accessibility of the service	Discounted and flexible fares,	FGC	2019
		Pay-per-use payment options	FGC	2019
		Subscription or monthly payment options	FGC	2019
	Security of the transport infrastructures	Number and typology of incidents	FGC	2019
		Presence and visibility of CCTV system	FGC	2019
		Presence and visibility of SOS emergency phone	FGC	2019
		Presence of police and security personnel	FGC	2019

Table 25 The list of retrieved structured open data and structured proprietary data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant metro and urban railway infrastructures managed by ZTM.

Data	Data typology	Indicators	Data Source	Year
Structured Open Data	Preliminary Data	Boundaries of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area	Website Warsaw Metropolis	2018

		Boundaries of the census section of the Mazowieckie Region	GIS Support Sp. z o.o.	2011
		Localization of the ZTM metro and commuter railway stations	GTFS Data Exchange	2019
	Territorial Data	Localization of urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
		Localization of points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Socio-demographic Data	Total population per census section	National Statistical Office	2011
		Age of population per census section	National Statistical Office	2011
		Gender of population per census section	National Statistical Office	2011
	Mobility Data	Localization of public transport services	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of road infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019

		Localization of parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Railway Network Data	Localization of ZTM lines	ZTM	2019
		Localization of ZTM tariff zones	ZTM	2019
		Infrastructure characteristics of the stations (i.e. underground or above ground)	ZTM	2019
		Characteristics of the territory surrounding the stations (city, town, village, countryside)	ZTM	2019
Structured Proprietary Data	Travel Demand Data	Number of passengers per stations per year	ZTM	2019
		Number of passengers per stations per month	ZTM	2019
	Reliability of the service	Percentage of trains on time (no delays or delays of less than 3 minutes)	ZTM	2019
		Operational hours and frequency of the service	ZTM	2019
	Accessibility of the service	Discounted and flexible fares,	ZTM	2019
		Pay-per-use payment options	ZTM	2019

		Subscription or monthly payment options	ZTM	2019
	Security of the transport infrastructures	Number and typology of incidents	ZTM	2019
		Presence and visibility of CCTV system	ZTM	2019
		Presence and visibility of SOS emergency phone	ZTM	2019
		Presence of police and security personnel	ZTM	2019

Structured Open Data Analysis (Use Case 1)

Figure 10 Quintile frequency distribution of territorial data related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the stations managed by FGC.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA
FGC stations (Province of Barcelona, Spain)

Figure 11 Quintile frequency distribution of socio-demographic data related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the stations managed by FGC.

Figure 12 Quintile frequency distribution of mobility data related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the stations managed by FGC.

Figure 13 Quintile frequency distribution of territorial data related to the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) and the stations managed by ZTM.

Figure 14 Quintile frequency distribution of socio-demographic data related to the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) and the stations managed by ZTM.

Figure 15 Quintile frequency distribution of mobility data related to the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) and the stations managed by ZTM.

Structured Open Data Results (Use Case I)

Table 26 Structured open data results related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the positively relevant stations managed by FGC.

FGC stations	Sarrià	Pàdua	Pl. Espanya	Sant Cugat	Can Ros
Metro	L6/L12	L7	L8		
Urban Railway	S1/S2/S5/S6/S7		S3/S4/S8/S9/R5/R50/R6/R60	S1/S2/S5/S6/S7	S3/S4/S8/S9/R5/R6
ZONES	I	I	I	2C	2B
Branch	EAST	EAST	WEST	EAST	WEST
Urban Fabric Km2 on buffer	0,618	0,954	0,447	0,640	0,535
Norm_Urban Fabric on buffer	0,849	0,996	0,590	0,872	0,739
POI No. On buffer	84	86	131	77	190
Norm_POI	0,685	0,693	0,855	0,654	0,963
TERRITORIAL DATA INDEX	0,920	0,962	0,883	0,917	0,965
Population density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	12,426,125	15,257,551	7,928,126	4,771,008	6,818,498

Norm_Population density on buffer_urban fabric	0,948	0,986	0,757	0,518	0,680
Female density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	6,730,155	8,115,170	4,308,519	2,536,523	3,542,689
Norm_Female density on buffer_urban fabric	0,953	0,986	0,770	0,522	0,671
Elderly density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	2,316,380	3,047,207	1,420,009	716,440	844,055
Norm_Elderly density on buffer_urban fabric	0,928	0,986	0,716	0,448	0,499
Foreginers density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	1,443,735	1,848,124	1,492,011	901,988	378,044
Norm_Foreginers density on buffer_urban fabric	0,877	0,958	0,890	0,657	0,372
SOCIO-DEMO DATA INDEX	0,944	0,961	0,856	0,586	0,647
Public Transports No. on buffer	17	13	26	6	24
Norm_Public Transports on buffer	0,953	0,852	0,999	0,481	0,997
Roads Km on buffer	11,970	9,053	16,375	12,672	15,677
Norm_Roads Km on buffer	0,613	0,373	0,887	0,668	0,856
Parking Services No. on buffer	5	4	9	6	4

Norm_Parking Services No. on buffer	0,845	0,749	0,991	0,912	0,749
MOBILITY DATA INDEX	0,955	0,846	0,991	0,834	0,977

Table 27 Structured open data results related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the negatively relevant stations managed by FGC.

FGC stations	Sant Joan	Igualada	El Palau	Martorell Enllac	Castellbell i el Vilar
Metro					
Urban Railway	S2/S6	R6/R60	S4/S8/R5/R6	S4/S8/R5/R6	R5
Tariff Zone	2C	6B	2B	3B	5E
Branch	EAST	WEST	WEST	WEST	WEST
Urban Fabric Km2 on buffer	0,009	0,495	0,015	0,028	0,056
Norm_Urban Fabric on buffer	0,033	0,676	0,035	0,041	0,054
POI No. On buffer	0	0	4	10	1
Norm_POI	0,291	0,291	0,308	0,334	0,295

TERRITORIAL DATA INDEX	0,065	0,514	0,071	0,082	0,073
Population density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	2,493	0,000	32,860	83,713	1,774
Norm_Population density on buffer_urban fabric	0,174	0,174	0,175	0,178	0,174
Female density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	1,275	0,000	16,197	42,165	0,861
Norm_Female density on buffer_urban fabric	0,179	0,178	0,180	0,183	0,179
Elderly density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	0,118	0,000	2,347	17,819	0,268
Norm_Elderly density on buffer_urban fabric	0,199	0,199	0,200	0,204	0,199
Foreginers density on buffer_urban fabric Km2	0,321	0,000	1,156	9,214	0,137
Norm_Foreginers density on buffer_urban fabric	0,197	0,197	0,197	0,200	0,197
SOCIO-DEMO DATA INDEX	0,163	0,163	0,164	0,167	0,163
Public Transports No. on buffer	2	0	2	0	1
Norm_Public Transports on buffer	0,303	0,163	0,251	0,163	0,204
Roads Km on buffer	10,041	8,696	4,411	5,095	8,119

Norm_Roads Km on buffer	0,454	0,345	0,098	0,125	0,302
Parking Services No. on buffer	2	0	0	0	0
Norm_Parking Services No. on buffer	0,494	0,242	0,242	0,242	0,242
MOBILITY DATA INDEX	0,388	0,145	0,107	0,085	0,149

Table 28 Structured open data results related to the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) and the positively relevant stations managed by ZTM.

ZTM stations	Warszawa Wilenska	Ratusz Arsenal	Zabki	Stoklosy	Plac Wilsona
Metro		M1		M1	M1
Urban railway	R60		R60		
Tariff Zone	I	I	2	I	I
Urban Fabric Km2	0,404	0,352	0,340	0,385	0,336
norm_Urban Fabric	0,696	0,335	0,745	0,172	0,506

POI	113	139	115	67	172
norm_POI	0,958	0,991	0,962	0,740	0,999
TERRITORIAL DATA INDEX	0,902	0,760	0,917	0,490	0,848
Population density on urban fabric on buffer	16,307,827	7,616,642	2,081,678	7,823,586	4,952,754
norm_Population density on urban fabric on buffer	1,000	0,874	0,350	0,885	0,659
Female density on urban fabric on buffer	8,578,829	4,298,746	1,126,400	4,166,620	2,740,352
norm_Female density on urban fabric on buffer	1,000	0,894	0,350	0,881	0,672
Elderly density on urban fabric on buffer	2,170,873	2,300,291	406,106	1,439,532	1,250,604
norm_Elderly density on urban fabric on buffer	0,960	0,972	0,335	0,802	0,731
SOCIO-DEMO DATA INDEX	0,972	0,943	0,337	0,927	0,781
Public Transport No. on Buffer	27	19	11	11	21

norm_Public Transport No. on Buffer	0,996	0,920	0,574	0,574	0,956
Roads Km on Buffer	18,537	25,107	19,347	20,839	25,851
norm_Roads Km on Buffer	0,816	0,968	0,845	0,891	0,975
Parking Service No. On Buffer	8	9	5	7	27
norm_Parking Service No. On Buffer	0,742	0,799	0,537	0,679	1,000
MOBILITY DATA INDEX	0,967	0,976	0,811	0,870	0,990

Table 29 Structured open data results related to the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) and the negatively relevant stations managed by ZTM.

ZTM stations	Warszawa Pludry	Warszawa Zaczisze - Wilno	Zalesie Gorne	Plochocin	Warszawa Wesola
Metro					
Urban railway	S3/S9/R9/R90/RL	R60	R8/RE8	R3/RE3	S2/R2/RE2
Tariff Zone	I	I	2	2	I

Urban Fabric Km2	0,185	0,129	0,236	0,246	0,240
norm_Urban Fabric	0,066	0,012	0,247	0,282	0,209
POI	1	17	6	0	6
norm_POI	0,180	0,296	0,213	0,174	0,213
TERRITORIAL DATA INDEX	0,114	0,136	0,204	0,202	0,185
Population density on urban fabric on buffer	174,429	354,419	88,390	577,738	1,523,199
norm_Population density on urban fabric on buffer	0,181	0,194	0,174	0,211	0,295
Female density on urban fabric on buffer	87,482	182,748	47,492	299,980	818,620
norm_Female density on urban fabric on buffer	0,179	0,192	0,174	0,209	0,294
Elderly density on urban fabric on buffer	26,537	60,802	19,599	83,943	294,099
norm_Elderly density on urban fabric on buffer	0,185	0,197	0,183	0,205	0,286

SOCIO-DEMO DATA INDEX	0,154	0,165	0,149	0,179	0,268
Public Transport No. on Buffer	8	7	3	1	7
norm_Public Transport No. on Buffer	0,394	0,336	0,151	0,091	0,336
Roads Km on Buffer	5,709	8,267	5,331	2,385	7,013
norm_Roads Km on Buffer	0,168	0,277	0,155	0,074	0,220
Parking Service No. On Buffer		1	1	1	
norm_Parking Service No. On Buffer	0,201	0,258	0,258	0,258	0,201
MOBILITY DATA INDEX	0,229	0,265	0,134	0,094	0,219

Annex 3 – Datasets related to Use Case III

Structured Open and Proprietary Data (Use Case III)

Table 30 The list of retrieved structured open data and structured proprietary data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant bike sharing docking stations managed by VELIB.

Data	Data typology	Indicators	Data Source	Year
Structured Open Data	Preliminary Data	Boundaries of the Paris Region (Petite Couronne)	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	2012
		Boundaries of the census section of the Paris Region	National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies	2019
		Localization of the VELIB bike sharing docking stations	Open platform for French public data	2019
	Territorial Data	Localization of urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
		Localization of points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Socio-demographic Data	Total population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Age of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Gender of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011

		Nationality of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
	Mobility Data	Localization of public transport services	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of cycleway infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Bike Sharing Docking Stations Network Data	Docking stations capacity (No. bikes)	Open platform for French public data	2019
Structured Proprietary Data	Travel Demand Data	Number of users per docking stations per year	VELIB	2019
		Number of users per docking stations per month	VELIB	2019
		Origin/destination matrix of the users	VELIB	2019
		Average length of trips	VELIB	2019
		Average time duration of trips	VELIB	2019
	Accessibility and Spontaneity	Number of public campaigns on cycling in the past year	VELIB	2019
		Number of adverts on bike-sharing services in the past year	VELIB	2019

	Do you need any requirement for signing-up for membership?	VELIB	2019
	Type of requirement for signing-up for membership (credit/debit card, internet access, smartphone...)	VELIB	2019
	Number and percentage of cash payment members (if applicable)	VELIB	2019
	The entry cost of bike-sharing scheme (upfront cost)	VELIB	2019
	Rental charges above one hour	VELIB	2019
	Annual membership cost of the scheme	VELIB	2019
	Types of safety gear supplied by operator (e.g. Helmet, hi-vis vest, raincoat etc.)	VELIB	2019
	Nature and type of insurance cover for bikes and users (i.e. damages, theft, accidents etc.) if available	VELIB	2019
	Number and percentage of docking stations at transport hubs	VELIB	2019
	Number and percentage of transport hubs with docking stations	VELIB	2019

		Number and percentage of low-income and minority neighbourhoods with docking stations	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of docking stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods	VELIB	2019
		Number and Percentage of Bike-sharing stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of bikes with a child seat, trailers and carriages for carrying children and goods	VELIB	2019
		The number of practical cycling programs/training (how to cycle with children and goods) held in the past year.	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of docking stations with shelter	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of docking stations with toilet facilities	VELIB	2019
	Safety and Security	Percentage of bike network segregated from vehicular traffic	VELIB	2019
		Number of cycling training programmes organised in a year to educate cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on	VELIB	2019

	the road		
	Number of public campaigns held to address harassment of cyclist in the past one year	VELIB	2019
	Number of public campaigns held to boost cyclists' confidence in the past one year	VELIB	2019
	Number and Percentage of docking stations with security devices (CCTV etc.)	VELIB	2019
	Number and Percentage of docking stations with CCTV	VELIB	2019
	Number and Percentage of bikes with well-functioning brakes, lights and reflectors etc.	VELIB	2019
	Number and Percentage of docking stations with information centres for users	VELIB	2019
	Speed limits on roads with cycle lanes (classified by road function)	VELIB	2019
	Percentage of roads with physically separated bike lanes from vehicular traffic	VELIB	2019
Social Constrains	Number of campaigns targeted at low-income and minority groups/neighbourhoods to promote	VELIB	2019

		cycling as an acceptable form of transport		
		Number of practical cycling training programmes	VELIB	2019
	Weather and Topography	Percentage of cycle network that is all-weather cycle friendly	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of electric bikes among bike fleet and at each docking station	VELIB	2019

Structured Open Data Analysis (Use Case III)

Figure 16 Quintile frequency distribution of territorial data related to the Paris Region (France) and the docking stations managed by VELIB.

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA
 VELIB docking points (Paris Region - Petite Couronne, France)

Figure 17 Quintile frequency distribution of socio-demographic data related to the Paris Region (France) and the docking stations managed by VELIB.

Figure 18 Quintile frequency distribution of mobility data related to the Paris Region (France) and the docking stations managed by VELIB.

Structured Open Data Results (Use Case III)

Table 31 Structured open data results related to the Paris Region (France) and the positively relevant docking stations managed by VELIB.

Docking Stations	Versailles - Claude Terrasse	Square Rena Viviani - Montebello	Godot de Mauroy - Madeleine	Charenton - Place du Col Bourgoin	Boyer-Barret - Raymond Losserand	Cita Riverin - Châteaudeau d'Eau	Faubourg Poissonniere - Delta	Halles - Bourdonnais	Guy Maquet - Saint-Ouen	Mathis - Flandre
<i>Docking Point_ID</i>	15401095	653050378	36391	82421013	214298601	95845524	1021553839	1057730786	365181481	78124875
<i>capacity</i>	46	34	22	35	23	18	36	20	53	55
<i>lat</i>	48,840	48,852	48,870	48,845	48,833	48,871	48,883	48,860	48,893	48,891
<i>lon</i>	2,264	2,348	2,326	2,383	2,317	2,359	2,350	2,346	2,327	2,376
<i>Urban Fabric Km2</i>	0,124	0,122	0,318	0,132	0,064	0,184	0,161	0,223	0,079	0,060
<i>Norm_Urban Fabric Km2 on Total Area</i>	0,786	0,456	0,839	0,814	0,763	0,742	0,727	0,745	0,826	0,828
<i>No. POI on census section</i>	96	326	357	188	56	255	243	544	62	63
<i>POI Density on Census Section Area</i>	640,314	1,655,296	975,057	1,207,598	704,717	1,095,905	1,178,711	1,937,966	669,681	904,426

<i>Norm_POI Density on Census Section Area</i>	0,617	0,991	0,836	0,927	0,666	0,890	0,918	0,998	0,639	0,798
TERRITORIAL DATA INDEX	0,824	0,849	0,940	0,956	0,839	0,927	0,932	0,957	0,859	0,926
<i>Population Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	4,910,506	3,935,356	3,462,193	6,405,452	3,164,285	5,491,507	6,269,308	5,471,170	4,360,723	3,331,727
<i>Norm_Population Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,954	0,857	0,777	0,996	0,717	0,980	0,995	0,980	0,910	0,752
<i>Female Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	2,730,490	2,177,918	1,815,086	3,476,291	1,750,472	2,901,320	3,098,762	2,765,326	2,394,690	1,609,595
<i>Norm_Female Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,968	0,883	0,774	0,997	0,750	0,981	0,989	0,971	0,927	0,693
<i>Elderly Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	3,573,183	3,013,765	2,979,793	5,427,468	2,658,447	4,429,330	5,230,047	4,410,067	3,573,505	2,911,729
<i>Norm_Elderly Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,917	0,827	0,820	0,998	0,746	0,980	0,996	0,980	0,917	0,806
<i>Foreigners Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	609,087	627,428	540,470	826,026	518,904	1,130,040	1,142,367	572,353	518,347	871,379
<i>Norm_Foreigners Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,862	0,877	0,796	0,973	0,771	0,999	0,999	0,829	0,771	0,982

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA INDEX	0,972	0,950	0,906	0,986	0,868	0,986	0,987	0,974	0,952	0,933
<i>No. Public Transport on census section</i>	10	12	45	10	4	18	21	44	6	4
<i>Public Transport density on census section</i>	66,699	60,931	122,906	64,234	50,337	77,358	101,864	156,747	64,808	57,424
<i>Norm_Public Transport density on census section</i>	0,847	0,796	0,998	0,827	0,680	0,917	0,987	1,000	0,832	0,761
<i>Km cycleway on census section</i>	1,380	2,384	1,584	1,488	1,460	6,390	2,685	5,240	0,924	0,592
<i>Km cycleway density on census section</i>	9,205	12,105	4,326	9,558	18,373	27,462	13,024	18,667	9,980	8,499
<i>Norm_Km cycleway density on census section</i>	0,728	0,858	0,429	0,746	0,981	1,000	0,889	0,983	0,768	0,689
MOBILITY DATA INDEX	0,931	0,952	0,872	0,930	0,954	0,989	0,985	0,992	0,938	0,883

Table 32 Structured open data results related to the Paris Region (France) and the negatively relevant docking stations managed by VELIB.

Docking Stations	Sorbonne - Ecoles	Mahatma Gandhi	Serrurier	Louis Pasteur - Albert Petit	Clichy - Douai	Chateau de Vincennes	Gare de Lyon - Van Gogh	Porte de la Plaine	Gare RER les Grasillons	Rond-Point Rhin et Danube
<i>Docking Point_ID</i>	66491368	221038698	42950839	102343591	653087180	66491396	291354793	27363205	1057373549	82588656
<i>capacity</i>	50	26	18	31	32	52	51	35	0	53
<i>lat</i>	48,850	48,876	48,880	48,796	48,884	48,844	48,844	48,828	48,920	48,840
<i>lon</i>	2,343	2,264	2,398	2,317	2,329	2,439	2,370	2,292	2,315	2,228
<i>Urban Fabric Km2</i>	0,005	0,061	0,100	0,033	0,077	0,070	0,037	0,116	0,061	0,157
<i>Norm_Urban Fabric Km2 on Total Area</i>	0,004	0,129	0,279	0,002	0,012	0,023	0,050	0,375	0,083	0,304
<i>No. POI on census section</i>	16	47	15	104	25	17	28	7	67	3

<i>POI Density on Census Section Area</i>	129,452	299,327	77,173	21,345	44,214	47,707	207,114	34,618	369,616	10,099
<i>Norm_POI Density on Census Section Area</i>	0,229	0,345	0,198	0,168	0,180	0,181	0,279	0,174	0,400	0,162
TERRITORIAL DATA INDEX	0,039	0,115	0,115	0,028	0,032	0,034	0,062	0,151	0,118	0,111
<i>Population Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	24,518	959,038	902,531	14,219	530,196	539,498	492,666	843,260	730,718	986,328
<i>Norm_Population Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,076	0,201	0,191	0,075	0,133	0,134	0,128	0,181	0,163	0,206
<i>Female Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	6,996	491,381	465,187	2,473	270,927	285,133	261,482	417,900	386,366	524,400
<i>Norm_Female Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,076	0,198	0,189	0,075	0,132	0,136	0,130	0,174	0,165	0,209
<i>Elderly Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	19,345	807,927	724,253	10,436	460,974	431,631	373,657	679,971	606,015	741,108
<i>Norm_Elderly Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,078	0,212	0,194	0,077	0,142	0,137	0,127	0,184	0,169	0,197
<i>Foreigners Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	11,266	163,861	198,472	10,633	32,074	70,883	50,579	187,442	110,422	88,984

<i>Norm_Foreigners Density on Urban Fabric on Buffer Area</i>	0,112	0,265	0,311	0,111	0,128	0,162	0,143	0,296	0,202	0,180
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC DATA INDEX	0,070	0,167	0,178	0,070	0,093	0,102	0,095	0,166	0,126	0,140
<i>No. Public Transport on census section</i>	1	2	2	48	7	5	2	3	1	4
<i>Public Transport density on census section</i>	8,091	12,737	10,290	9,852	12,380	14,032	14,794	14,836	5,517	13,465
<i>Norm_Public Transport density on census section</i>	0,166	0,209	0,186	0,182	0,205	0,222	0,229	0,230	0,145	0,216
<i>Km cycleway on census section</i>	0,000	0,031	0,000	5,840	1,328	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
<i>Km cycleway density on census section</i>	0,000	0,197	0,000	1,199	2,349	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
<i>Norm_Km cycleway density on census section</i>	0,191	0,200	0,191	0,248	0,310	0,191	0,191	0,191	0,191	0,191
MOBILITY DATA INDEX	0,089	0,110	0,096	0,119	0,163	0,111	0,115	0,115	0,081	0,109

Annex 4 – Datasets related to Use Case IV

Structured Proprietary Data (Use Case IV)

Table 33 The list of structured proprietary data that were retrieved from FGC and ZTM and analysed for the UC IV.

Level 1	Level 2	Datasets	Notes
Socio-Economic Conditions	Job Segregation	Number of women employees	
		Number of men employees	
		Number of women who are managers	
		Number of men who are managers	A manager is a person who is responsible for a part of the organization, this may include supervising and managing a group of people
		Number of women who are directors	A member of the board of directors. A person holding a "directorship" in a legal sense, who is a board member and has specific legal duties and responsibilities for management of the company
		Number of men who are directors	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
	Policy/Legal	Number of men working part time	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).

		Number of women working part time	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of employees with caring responsibilities	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of women normally working flexibly (including home working and flexible start and finish times) [pre-COVID-19]	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of women normally working flexibly (including home working and flexible start and finish times) [post-COVID-19]	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of men normally working flexibly (including home working and flexible start and finish times) [pre=COVID-19]	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of men normally working flexibly (including home working and flexible start and finish times) [post=COVID-19]	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of women who took maternity leave (in the last 3 years)	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Number of men who took paternity leave (in the last 3 years)	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
		Average duration (months) of maternity leave taken by women in the last 3 years?	
Socio-Economic Conditions	Policy/Legal	Number of women employees who are disabled	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).

		Number of men employees who are disabled	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
Job Characteristics	HR Policies	Number of employees currently on zero hours contracts	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
Socio-Economic Conditions	Job Segregation	Average salary (per month or year) of all women employees	
		Average salary (per month or year) of all men employees	
		Ratio of salary women/men of employees	Please complete if the questions above are not given confidentiality reasons
		Average salary (per month or year) of all women managers	
		Average salary (per month or year) of all men managers	
		Ratio of salary women/men of managers	Please complete if the questions above are not given for confidentiality reasons
		Average salary (per month or year) of all women directors	
		Average salary (per month or year) of all male directors	

		Ratio of salary women/men of directors	Please complete if the questions above are not given for confidentiality reasons
Job Characteristics	HR Policies	Number new female employees (in the last 3 years)	
		Number new male employees (in the last 3 years)	
		Number new female managers (in the last 3 years)	
		Number new male managers (in the last 3 years)	
		Number new female directors (in the last 3 years)	
		Number new male directors (in the last 3 years)	
		Number of women non-managers who have been promoted (internally) in the last 3 years	Promotion is defined as: the advancement of an employee from one job to another job with a higher salary rank and/or and higher-level job responsibilities
		Number of men non-managers who have been promoted in the last 3 years	
		Number of women who have been promoted to managers in the last 3 years	

		Number of men who have been promoted in the last 3 years	
		Number of women who have been promoted to directors in the last 3 years	
		Number of men who have been promoted to directors in the last 3 years	
		Number of recruitment campaigns targeted to women (in the last 3 years)	
		Is there a person or body in charge of developing and monitoring actions to advance the position of women within the company? (i.e., an equality and diversity manager)	Yes/No
	Terms And Conditions	Does your company normally have safety equipment (CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-theft equipment, closed cabins etc.) to protect drivers and other personnel from aggressive third-party behaviour?	Yes/No (Yes= the company normally has any (one or more) safety equipment, No= the company does not have any)
	Female Facilities	Do you provide separate toilet facilities for ALL female employees? (if NO please give details)	Including operations staff and office staff
		Do you provide separate changing facilities for ALL females? (if NO please give details)	Including operations staff and office staff
	Training Provision	Number of flexible training systems (e.g., online courses, courses with flexible timetable, etc.) [pre-COVID-19]	
		Is the training evaluated? (Yes/No)	Yes/No

	Safety And Security	Number of communications about zero tolerance provided to the workforce (in the last 3 years)	
		On a scale of 1-10, are security staff available to intervene in case of need at all times	Please provide a numerical response (1=never, 10=always)
Personal Circumstances	Caring And Parenting Responsibilities	Number of people with young children (approx. under 5 years) who have requested a change of shifts or reduced working time (in the last 3 years)	
		Number of people with young children (approx. under 5 years) who have been given a change of shifts or reduced working time (in the last 3 years)	
	Economic Deprivation	Minimum hourly rate for low skilled part-time work (Euro/hour)	
Individual Characteristics	Health Status And Wellbeing	Number of women who have resigned claiming caring responsibilities as the reason (in the last 3 years)	* If numbers are too small and cannot be given for confidentiality reasons, then give number in bands of 5 (e.g., 1-5, 6-10 etc).
	Skills	Is training in your organisation provided external training providers? (Yes/No)	This question refers to training delivered by external organisations to the business
	Job Segregation	How many staff have received training courses which focus on avoiding cultural stereotypes (last 3 years)	
		Does your organisation have procedures to review the fairness/equity in recruitment processes? (Yes/No)	Yes/No
	Demand Factors	Does the organisation conduct targeted recruitment campaigns to seek to reduce occupational segregation by gender? (Yes/No)	Yes/No

		Does your organisation operate a gender neutral recruitment policy? (Yes/No)	Yes/No
		Is recruitment designed to attract both men and women? (Yes/No)	Yes/No
		Please list the most common methods/platforms/channels currently used to advertise vacancies to those outside your organisation	(e.g., websites, magazines, industry journals etc.)

